

**"A NECESSITY TO UPGRADE THE IT LEARNING TO A FINER VERSION
IN ACCOUNTING STREAM."**

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Abstract :

The efficiency of the accounting practices and the factors that affects the use of information technology covers large aspects. Accounting practices covers so many factors for example ranging from profession, statutory and a host of multiple other factors but this study is restricted to cover the usage of information technology within accounting professionals and accounting students and also on the gap between education and employment. Provide information about new technologies to the accounting professionals and accounting students. In this new era there are lot of technologies are introduced. Better utilization of information technology for accounting students. This study will explain the how accountants and accounting students can use the information technology for their job and for their studies. Findings from this study will also prove useful to students and academician concerning the teaching and learning aids. This study is very useful for the accounting students and the prevailing educational system. They will get lot of information from this research which will enhance their skills.

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Introduction :

Advancements in information technology have efficiently enhanced the accounting systems and transformed economic life. Every accountant identifies that accounting is the language of corporate. The language of accounting has gone through many changes from time to time. Information Technology has always plays important role in making the accountants and accounting student's life easier. Students of accounting can also make the better utilization of information technology for their study for example they can learn so many information technology courses available in the market such as Tally, Excel which enhance the ability and knowledge of students. Overall, technology has caused a major twist in the accounting profession. Hiring trends, educational needs, and the rise of the consulting side of accounting are just some of the impacts that technology has had on the accounting profession. These cannot be said as benefits or disadvantages. It is clear, that these impacts as well as the advantages and disadvantages are forcing a change in the profession of accounting. The efficiency of the accounting practices and the factors that affects the use of information technology covers large aspects. IT has already been integrated in accounting stream but the practical aspects are still lacking or not yet updated.

Statement Of Problem :

Most of the accounting students have knowledge about the information technology. Now a days every accounting students use internet on their mobile phones or on laptops, but have less knowledge of accounting softwares. While perusing accounting studies students should complete their all the technical qualification, but they don't even bother about these courses. In the world of information technology there are so many new courses available for the accountants but they don't even know about this. There are number of software's are available for the accountants which will make their work or job very easy but they don't have knowledge about these software's. This study will evaluate the degree of IT acceptance by accounting professionals in the preparation and presentation of financial reported accounts. To what extent are accountant's preparations literate with the use of information technology? How relevant is information technology in today's accounting profession?

Objective Of Study :

- To understand the importance of information technology in the profession of accountancy.
- To measure the knowledge of IT among accounting students.
- To evaluate the importance of IT on integration to education.

Scope Of Study :

The world is revolving around the IT. In this modern era, the world is wanting for people are excellent in the field of IT. IT ha replaced all the manual works. The study focus on the bridge between the knowledge of Information Technology among accounting students and the accounting education provided.

Limitation :

- a. The study is limited to the time, scope and cost with which we could not collect more samples. Thus, the research was only conducted in Kalyan City.
- b. The sample collected is limited in population within the area of Kalyan, so the research may not satisfy the thinking and expectations of those public who are from different cities other than Mumbai.
- c. The questionnaire might have excluded some other factors; the questions which were released for this project work may be not been able to cover all the factors according to the research

Research Methodology :

This research was conducted to get the information related to the usage of information technology for accounting professional and accounting students. The research design adopted was descriptive.

- a. Primary : The information is to be collected from Google form through questionnaire method.
- b. Secondary : The study is proved in the light of secondary information with the use of journals, articles, books, etc.
- c. Sampling size: The population from which information is collected are accounting students and professionals approximately 100. The information is collected will be specifically from Kalyan city.

Review Of Literature :

1. According to Chua, in adoption of Information technology, now days internet uses has increased so the students and accountants know the various facts about internet, about security. This has exposed individuals, organizations and full countries to significant threats, and Theft of digital information has become the foremost commonly reported fraud, surpassing physical theft, and up to date research indicates that the comparative insecurity of small and medium-sized enterprises is making them an increasing focus for cyber-attacks. (Chua, 2013)
2. According to Lim, Nowadays, information technology has become time saving, it introduced number of software's which use accountants in numerous ways. The accounting software's uses accountants to save their time at workplace. Because, it provides automate accounting procedures and reduces the mistakes of book maintaining. (lim, 2013)
3. According to Alfahad, Information technology uses in reduction of the usage of paper in the business of accounting, now everything done electronically so there is no use of paper. Maintaining the hard copy records of the accounting activities and financial reports. Moving accounting books towards a digital format can use accountants to maintain the financial information in organized form and also use them to recover important information with ease.(Alfahad, 2012)
4. According to Alves, Information technology uses accountants to reduce the amount of errors. If we talk about simple and normal thing such as spelling mistake and grammar mistakes can be fixed using word processing and software like Microsoft word. If an accountant is emerging an important document for the investors. Now, with the use of computer technology, accountant can provide their best foot forward to impress investors rather than diverting those errors. (Alves, 2010)
5. According to Yadav Information technology uses in the computations. Since, we know accounting task is very comprehensive and detailed, accuracy in recording the transactions and reporting it to the organization is greatly valued. (Yadav, August 2016)
6. According to Ghasemi, Shafeipour, Aslani, and Barvayeh, Information technologies have also enhanced the functionality of accounts departments by increasing the timeliness of accounting information. Information technology reduced the time of performing work of the accountants.(Maziyar Ghasemi a, 2011)
7. According to Al-Khadash and Al-Bishtawi Accounting software's uses students in so many ways Accountants must be aware with the software tools to use them to accomplish the accounting functions more effectively and efficiently. There are so many accounting software tools available for accounting students and also for professional accountants. (Al-Bishtawi, 2010)
8. According to Bahador, Haider and Mohd Saman, Information technology competencies are authoritative for the accountants to perform their task, IT experience, and the skills of management and interpersonal skills. These skills of accountants on one hand benefit the routine activities of business related to work of accountants and this also indicates the changing atmosphere of the work of accountants and corresponding information technology skills. (Ku Maisurah Ku Bahador, 2012)

9. According to Dalahmeh, Uses of IT uses accounting graduates to get better job. Nowadays accounting graduates are more mature and have knowledge about each and everything which use them to develop their career. Accounting students now more focused on their career. That's the reason that they are doing all the technological courses which use them to get better job in any organization. (El-Dalahmeh, April 2017)

Data Analysis And Interpretation :

Profession (Working stream)

The respondents from accounting professionals are 51 respondents are accounting professionals, working under different streams of accounting. The stream considered was- Academician, Accountant, Auditing, Taxation, Banking and others. The responses received for these streams were like Academician-6, Accountant-11, Auditing-6, Taxation-7, Banking-6, Other-15.

Do you agree use of computerized accounting system helps accountants to keep proper accounting records?

The chart is related to the usage of computerized accounting system can help accountants to keep proper accounting records. Maximum number of accountants says that computerized accounting system helps to keep proper accounting records and all are agreeing with the statement.

Do you think IT ensures a better and secured way of compiling accounting works?

The chart is related to the question that whether the IT ensures a better and secured way of compiling accounting works. Majority of the respondents' i.e.41.20% also agrees that Information Technology ensures a better and secured way of compiling accounting records.

According to you, should professionals have all the knowledge about IT mechanism before entering to corporate?

Accounting professionals

← Accounting students

It was asked to the accounting professionals and the students that whether an accounting student should know all the Information Technology mechanism before entering to the corporate world and the majority respondents agrees with the statement only two of the respondents disagrees.

Does the integration of IT skills with accounting stream will improve the quality of learning?

← Accounting professional

← Accounting student

With this responses obtained from the accounting professionals as well as students, we can state than an accounting student should be given a basic information technology knowledge and they are willing for it. It was asked that the integration of IT skills with accounting stream will improve the quality of learning. Majority of the respondents strongly agrees with the statement. With this the importance and the improvement in education can be improved by integrating IT with the stream.

Rank your knowledge concerning IT before and after being a profession.

← Before working

There was a ranking question asked to the accounting professionals. The question was before being a professional and after being a professional. It was seen in the received data that the knowledge concerning IT was low and then after entering to the corporate or professional field each and every respondent has increased their knowledge. Do you agree that education in IT can help accounting students diversify and get a better job opportunity?

← Accounting student

It was asked to the working accounting professionals and accounting students that whether education in information technology can provide a better job opportunities for the upcoming professionals the majority response is positive. They also agreed that information technology can give diversified opportunities for accountants in the corporate world.

Does the education provided concerning IT is sufficient?

68% i.e. more than half of the respondents are not satisfied with the education concerning IT provided in the curriculum which means there is an important issue prevailing in the system.

Conclusion :

The data is collected from accounting professionals to compare the knowledge and to know the importance of practical aspects of accounting professionals with the help of IT. As per the above analysis we can conclude that accounting students and accounting professionals understands the usage of information technology. IT always helps students to get the real corporate job related knowledge. Every student should use IT for their better future, because it provides a lot of information about their career. For professional accountants IT is a great source of knowledge by using IT they can make their job easier. The respondents also agrees that accounting procedures should be customised or modified by integrating IT.

Accounting syllabus is very important while working as an accounting professional. The theory and practical knowledge students get during their academic they use that knowledge into the corporate world also. Information Technology syllabus provides students the foundation of accounting. If we see from the data analysis most of the respondents are agreeing that Integration of IT in accountancy is important. Financial accounts, Management accounts, cost accounting these are the some example of the syllabus of accounting. These subjects can helps us to learn in theory as well as in practical also. IT will help students to get practical knowledge about these subjects. Accounting should be taught practically in institutions because practical knowledge is important for the students because that practical knowledge student will put into their job while working as a professional. The education should be combined with vocational or practical education. Whereas now it is still lacking behind to in regards to practical learning. There is major need for refining the prevailing education system.

Thus from the entire data collected and with the help of the analysis it suggests that IT is a vital factor and it should be modified by integrating it in the prevailing syllabus which can help the accounting students to become proficient and to excel in their field

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